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Equilibrium Study of the Ternary Complexes of Copper-, Nickel- and Cobalt-(II) with 2,2'-Dipyridyl/*o*-Phenanthroline) and Salicylidene-2-iminopyridine†

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THE present communication deals with the potentiometric study on the complex forming equilibria involved in the ternary complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy) or *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) as the primary ligand (A) and the Schiff base salicylidene-2-iminopyridine (SAP) as the secondary ligand (LH) in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 30° and ionic strength, $I=0.1\text{ M}$ (KNO_3) adopting Irving-Rossotti method¹ as modified by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya².

Experimental

The Schiff base salicylidene-2-iminopyridine was prepared as described earlier³ and dissolved in lime-distilled alcohol to make 0.02 M solution of the ligand. A ECIL 5651 digital pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit), with a combined glass electrode assembly was used for pH-measurement. pH-metric titration technique was followed⁴ for the determination of formation constant values. The following solutions were prepared and titrated against standard alkali solution at 30° in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength, $I=0.1\text{ M}$ (KNO_3): (a) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M SAP + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (b) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy (*o*-phen) + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (c) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (d) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy (*o*-phen) + 0.1 M KNO_3 , (e) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy (*o*-phen) + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.1 M KNO_3 , and (f) 0.02 M HNO_3 ,

+ 0.1 M KNO_3 . In each case, the total volume was 50 ml. Representative titration curves are shown in Fig. 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated using standard expressions^{1,2}. The results are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Mixed-ligand titration curve of Cu-dipy-SAP system: (a) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M SAP, (b) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP, (c) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M metal nitrate + 0.002 M SAP, (d) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy, (e) 0.02 M HNO_3 + 0.002 M dipy + 0.002 M metal nitrate and (f) 0.02 M HNO_3 ; temp. = 30°; $I=0.1\text{ M}$ KNO_3 (total volume = 50 ml); B = pH meter reading.

Results and Discussion

An observation of the mixed-ligand system (Cu-dipy-SAP) (Fig. 1) reveals that metal-dipyridyl curve (e) diverges from dipyridyl curve (d) at low pH indicating that metal-dipyridyl complex formation takes place at low pH. Calculation of \bar{n} shows that complete formation of 1:1 metal-dipy complex takes place at $\text{pH} \leq 4$. This remains stable upto $\text{pH} \approx 6$, after which metal-dipy curve diverges from the dipy-curve showing formation of hydroxo-species $[\text{M}(\text{dipy})(\text{OH})_n]$. After $\text{pH} \approx 9$, the com-

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TABLE 1 - STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY (ML) AND TERNARY (MAL) COMPLEXES IN 50% (V/V) ETHANOL - WATER MEDIUM

Temp = 30°, I = 0.1 M (KNO₃).

Cation	log K_{ML}^M	log $K_{ML_2}^{ML}$	log $K_{M-dipy-L}^{M-dipy}$	log $K_{M-o-phen-L}^{M-o-phen}$	$\Delta \log K_M$ L = o-phen(dipy)
Cu ²⁺	6.65	4.60	6.60	6.50	-0.15 (-0.05)
Ni ²⁺	4.70	3.38	4.44	4.31	-0.39 (-0.26)
Co ²⁺	4.53	3.48	4.11	4.11	-0.42 (-0.42)

pK_{OH}, 9.13; pK_{NH+}, 6.58.

plex decomposes and seems to form the metal hydroxides that precipitate out. Metal-dipy-SAP and metal-dipy curves overlap at low pH which shows that combination of the secondary ligand does not take place in the pH range where metal-primary ligand combination takes place. Mixed-ligand titration curve (b) diverges from the secondary ligand titration curve (a) at a pH above the complete formation of 1:1 metal-dipy complex and below the commencement of hydroxo-complex formation. Further, in the titration of the mixed-ligand system (curve b) no precipitate appears even after pH ≈ 9 and this indicates the formation of mixed-ligand complex. It may be assumed that the secondary ligand (SAP) would combine with metal-dipy complex species in ternary system just as it does with [M(H₂O)_n]²⁺ in the simple system. Similar observations have also been made when o-phenanthroline was used as the primary ligand instead of dipyrindyl. The values of log K_{MAL}^{MAL} have been determined using (i) half \bar{n} -method and (ii) pointwise calculation method⁴. The two values agree closely, and the mean of these two values is given in Table 1.

Unlike our earlier observation⁵, it is found that in the present case log $K_{ML}^M \approx \log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$ (A = dipy or o-phen). The two nitrogen atoms of the dipyrindyl (o-phenanthroline) molecule besides forming σ -bonds with the metal ions, participate in M→L ($d\pi-p\pi$) interaction⁶. Due to this back-donation the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in [M(dipy)]²⁺ can not increase significantly and hence the tendency of [M(aq)]²⁺ or [M(dipy)]²⁺ to receive the secondary ligand remains nearly the same and this justifies log $K_{ML}^M \approx \log K_{MAL}^{MAL}$. The lower value of log $K_{ML_2}^{ML}$ than log K_{MAL}^{MAL} is however expected on the basis of coulombic repulsions⁶ exerted between the secondary ligand anions. For 1:1:1 mixed ligand complexes, the observed order of stability, Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ is the same as for the corresponding M-L systems. The plot of log K_{MAL}^{MAL} against log K_{ML}^M is a straight line suggesting⁷ that addition of the secondary ligand (L) to the (metal-dipy/o-phen) species follows the same trend as in the association of L to M²⁺(aq) ions in the binary system. The $\Delta \log K$ values⁸ are negative (Table 1) Similar $\Delta \log K$ values of mixed chelates involving

2,2'-dipyrindyl and "mixed donor" O-N atoms were obtained by Griesser and Sigel⁹.

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Polarographic Study of the Formation of Ternary Complexes of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) with Oxalate, Citrate, Salicylate or Benzoate and Pyruvate

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THE paper describes the possibility of the formation of ternary complexes of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with oxalate, citrate, salicylate or benzoate as primary ligand and pyruvate as the secondary ligand using polarographic technique.